

Performance Of Employees Procurement Of Goods And Services In The Riau Islands Province Through Job Satisfaction With Transformational Leadership As Moderating

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ABSTRACT

Keywords:

Task Complexity, Competence, Work Culture, Locus of Control, Job Satisfaction, Transformational Leadership and Procurement Performance.

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The aim of this research is to analyze the direct influence between task complexity, competence, work culture and locus of control on the performance of goods and services procurement employees and to analyze the indirect influence between task complexity, competence, work culture and locus of control on the work of goods and services procurement employees. services which are moderated by the transformational leadership variable. The number of samples is the same as the population or by census or saturated sample method, as many as 163 employees managing the procurement of goods and services for the Riau Islands Province (PPK and Election Working Group). The data analysis method was carried out using descriptive statistics and data analysis using SEM and data processing using the smart PLS program. The R Square value of the combined or simultaneous influence of X1, X2, X3, and X4 on Y is 0.907 with an adjusted R Square value of 0.903. This can be explained that all exogenous constructs (X1, X2, X3, and X4) simultaneously influence Z by 90.30%. These findings prove that task complexity, competence, work culture and locus of control have a significant determination of the performance of procurement of goods and services in the Riau Islands Province and have an R Square value of combined or simultaneous influence of X1, X2, X3, and X4 on Z of 0.769 with an adjusted R Square value of 0.763. This proves that task complexity, competence, work culture and locus of control have significant determinants of job satisfaction of 76.30%. And the R Square value of the moderating effect on the performance of goods and services procurement employees is 0.775 with an adjusted R Square value of 0.770, meaning that the transformational leadership variable has an influence on the performance of goods and services procurement employees by 77%. The novelty of this research is that to optimize the performance of procurement of goods and services in the Riau Islands Province, researchers added one indicator to the locus of control variable, namely the need for spiritual intelligence (ESQ) in addition to emotional intelligence.

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Introduction

The development of bureaucracy in Indonesia recently has not improved, as desired by bureaucratic reform, this is characterized by still weak bureaucracy, complicated bureaucracy, lack of transparency and accountability. Therefore, it is time for the bureaucracy to be completely reformed, so

that the public's need for services for the services provided by the government gets better from time to time. As mandated by the Ministry of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform, the State Civil Apparatus in serving them must have morals, that is, they must be service oriented, accountable, competent, harmonious, loyal, adaptive and collaborative, in this way the bureaucracy is expected to recover quickly from adversity. Therefore, we need to prepare Human Resources (HR) who are competent and professional so that these problems can be overcome. The preparation of Human Resources (HR) in the field of managing procurement of goods and services is no exception, in accordance with the Circular Letter of the Government Goods and Services Procurement Policy Institute (LKPP) Number 8 of 2020 concerning Typology of Commitment Making Officials and Competency Standards for Procurement of Government Goods/Services For Commitment Making Officials, officials who manage the procurement of goods and services are required to have the competency as regulated in the regulation in question. However, until now the availability of Human Resources (HR) as intended is not yet available in the Riau Islands Provincial Government, currently the competency typology of procurement managers goods and services, namely Commitment Making Officials are still in typology C, while typologies A and B are not yet available, this is a challenge for the Riau Islands Provincial Government to improve the competence of its Human Resources in order to fulfill the requirements mandated by these provisions. This is in line with research conducted by Annisa Putri Soetrisno (2018), which stated that competency has a significant effect on employee performance at PT. Telekomunikasi Indonesia Tbk Witel Bandung. The magnitude of the influence is 51%, meaning it shows that the competency variable has an influence on employee performance variables.

Apart from problems in human resources in the procurement of goods and services in the Riau Islands Province, there are still Budget Users (PA) or Budget User Authorities (KPA) who still serve as Commitment Making Officials (PPK) in terms of the PPK's duties being very technical, so if still holding the same position as PA/KPA certainly requires a lot of time and must have competence in the technical field, while PA/KPA who also hold the position as PPK are not required to have a typology competency certificate as mentioned, they only need to have a basic level certificate, by Therefore, to develop and increase the competence of PPK so that it has expertise in the PPK typology, it is time for PPK to be separated from the description of PA/KPA. Based on this, we see that the level of work complexity is still very high in the Riau Islands Province, especially in the governance of the goods and services procurement process. Suarni Norawati (2022), Competence and motivation have a significant effect on performance through locus of control. This means that the more competence, motivation and work discipline possessed by employees, the locus of control will also increase and performance will also increase, thus locus of control can mediate the influence of competence on employee performance, but work discipline is not proven to have a significant effect on performance through LOC.

Based on the description above, the problem in this research can be formulated as:

- 1) How does task complexity influence job satisfaction in the Riau Islands Province
- 2) How does competence influence job satisfaction in the Riau Islands Province
- 3) How does work culture influence job satisfaction in the Riau Islands Province
- 4) How does locus of control influence job satisfaction in the Riau Islands Province
- 5) What is the influence of job satisfaction on the performance of employees procuring goods and services in the Riau Islands Province
- 6) How does task complexity affect the performance of goods and services procurement employees in the Riau Islands Province?
- 7) How does competence influence the performance of employees procuring goods and services in the Riau Islands Province?
- 8) How does work culture influence the performance of employees procuring goods and services in the Riau Islands Province
- 9) How does locus of control influence the performance of goods and services procurement employees in the Riau Islands Province
- 10) How is the influence of task complexity on the performance of goods and services procurement employees mediated by job satisfaction in the Riau Islands Province
- 11) What is the influence of competency on the performance of goods and services procurement employees mediated by job satisfaction in the Riau Islands Province

- 12) What is the influence of work culture on the performance of employees procuring goods and services which is mediated by job satisfaction in the Riau Islands Province
- 13) How is the influence of locus of control on the performance of goods and services procurement employees mediated by job satisfaction in the Riau Islands Province
- 14) What is the influence of job satisfaction on the performance of goods and services procurement employees moderated by Transformational leadership in the Riau Islands Province

Literature Review

Task Complexity (X1)

Task complexity is a task that is unstructured, difficult to understand and ambiguous in the process according to Puspitasari. The level of task complexity will influence the results of performance due to the large amount of information that must be processed by employees and the stages of work that must be carried out to complete a job. Task complexity is the difficulty of a task caused by limited capabilities, memory and the ability to integrate problems possessed by a decision maker (Jamilah, et al, 2007). According to Bonner, the complexity of tasks in carrying out work needs to be carried out. Research because there are three basic reasons for conducting testing. First, an employee's performance is significantly influenced by the level of task complexity. Second, decision making has been conditioned in such a way in the form of certain tools, techniques and training to understand the peculiarities of the complexity of employee tasks. Third, the company's employee team can find the best solution for employees and work because they understand the complexity of a task.

Competency (X2)

According to McClelland in Sudarmayanti (20017) defines competence as a fundamental characteristic possessed by a person that directly influences, or can describe, excellent performance. In other words, competence is what outstanding performers do more often in more situations with better results, than what average performers do. (Zainal, Veithzal Rivai, et al. 2015, p.230). Meanwhile, a competent ASN can be reflected in mastering their field of work, being focused, innovative, creative, responsive, communicative, experienced, results-oriented and trustworthy (according to Asman Abnur, 2017). Competence or also called ability or a person's capacity to carry out various tasks in a job according to their field of competence and is related to the effectiveness of individual performance in their work. Competence is a person's personality characteristic, which reflects a person's characteristics, whether he has the concept of self-development, knowledge and skills, so that he has advantages compared to other people. In this research, the competency variables that will be used to measure Ruky's competency in Fadillah (2017), namely personal character, self-concept, knowledge and skills, and skills or strengths and work motivation.

Work Culture (X3)

Organizational culture usually involves all experiences, philosophies, experiences, expectations, and all values within it. Thus, this organizational culture will be reflected through their daily activities, starting from their interactions with other people, the way they work and their expectations for the future. According to Linton, culture is the totality of attitudes and patterns of behavior. And knowledge, describes a habit that is inherited and owned by a member of society or a certain group of members. Kreitner and Kinicki (2005). Effat Al-Syarqawi defines culture from an Islamic religious perspective, Culture is a historical treasure of a group of people which is reflected in testimonies and various values which outline that a life must have spiritual meaning and purpose. Lathans believes that organizational culture is the norms and values that lead to the behavior of organizational members. All members will behave in accordance with the prevailing culture in order to be accepted by their environment. According to William H. Haviland, culture is a set of rules and norms that are shared by a group of members or members of society. If done by these people, it will give rise to behavior that is considered worthy or acceptable by all in society.

Locus of Control (X4)

According to Philip Kotler, personality is a differentiated innate characteristic of human psychology (human psychological traits) that produces relatively consistent and long-lasting responses to environmental

stimuli.1 Personality is usually described in terms of behavioral characteristics such as self-confidence, dominance, sociability, autonomy, and ways of defending self, adaptability, and aggressiveness. 2 Things related to personality are self-concept. Self-concept is an individual's view and attitude towards themselves. Self-view is related to physical dimensions, individual characteristics, and self-motivation. Self-concept is the core of an individual's personality. The core of personality plays an important role in determining and directing personality development and positive individual behavior. Locus of control is one of the concepts of individual personality in organizational behavior. The basic concept of locus of control is taken from social learning theory developed by Rotter (Patten, 2005).

Job Satisfaction (Z1)

According to Robbins and Coulter (2012:403) job satisfaction is an employee's general attitude towards their work. Locke in Luthans (2006: 243) provides a comprehensive definition of job satisfaction which includes cognitive, affective and evaluative reactions or attitudes and states that job satisfaction is a happy emotional state or positive emotion that comes from an assessment of one's work or work experience. According to Colquitt, et.al, (2011) that job satisfaction is the level of pleasant feelings obtained from assessing one's work or work experience. Meanwhile, McShane and VonGlinow (2010) view job satisfaction as a person's evaluation of their work and the work context. It is an assessment of job characteristics, work environment, and perceived emotional experiences at work. The work environment is part of the driving aspect of employee job satisfaction. The previous statement is also supported by the opinion of Robbins & Judge (2015) which explains that working conditions that help employees' work can increase job satisfaction. Job satisfaction is a working condition that can help employees complete

Transformational Leadership (Z2)

Transformational leadership can be a moderating variable that indirectly influences employee performance. Transformational leadership is a leadership style that aims to motivate, inspire, and encourage employees to innovate and create changes necessary for the company's future success. Transformational leaders can increase employee motivation and performance because they feel valued and have clear goals. Transformational leadership can influence employee performance positively both directly and indirectly by mediating job satisfaction. Transformational leadership practices can increase employee job satisfaction, commitment to the organization, and the effectiveness of HR practices in the organization.

According to Bass and Avolio, quoted from Yukl (2010), transformational leadership has four dimensions or characteristics, namely as follows: 1. Idealized influence (charismatic), namely a leader who has charisma and strength and great influence to motivate subordinates in carry out work. Subordinates trust leaders because leaders can show impressive behavior that makes leaders respected and can be an example for their followers. 2. Inspirational motivation (inspiration and motivation) is leader behavior that inspires and stimulates subordinates' enthusiasm for achievement, as well as demonstrating commitment to company goals and increasing subordinates' optimism and enthusiasm in achieving company goals. 3. Intellectual simulation (Intellectual Stimulation) is the behavior of leaders in creating new ideas to create progress in an organization and becoming a leader who is able to influence subordinates to find new perspectives which are expected to be able to solve problems that are or will be faced by an organization 4. Individualized Consideration, namely the willingness of the leadership to listen to suggestions from subordinates as well as the leadership's attention to the career development of employees and paying attention to the facilities obtained by employees so that good relationships can be established between superiors and subordinates.

Performance (Y)

Performance. The concept of performance is defined by Colquitt, LePine and Wesson (2009:37) as "the value of the set of employee behaviors that contribute, either positively or negatively, to organizational goal accomplishment" (the value of a set of employee behaviors that contribute, either positively or negatively towards fulfilling organizational goals). The success of an organization is influenced by performance, for this reason every company will try to improve employee performance in achieving predetermined organizational goals. The definition of performance is a work result produced by an employee that is interpreted to achieve the expected goals. According to Mangkunegara (2012:67),

performance is the result of work in terms of quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him.

Framework of thinking

Figure 1. Research Model

Research Hypothesis

Based on the data collected and analyzed through this research, the following hypothesis can be drawn:

1. Task complexity influences job satisfaction in the Riau Islands Province
2. Competency influences job satisfaction in the Riau Islands Province
3. Work culture influences job satisfaction in the Riau Islands Province
4. Locus of control influences work satisfaction in the Riau Islands Province
5. Job satisfaction influences the performance of procurement of goods and services in the Riau Islands Province
6. Task complexity influences the performance of procurement of goods and services in the Riau Islands Province
7. Competency influences the performance of procurement of goods and services in the Riau Islands Province
8. Work culture influences the performance of procurement of goods and services in the Riau Islands Province
9. Locus of control influences the performance of procurement of goods and services in the Riau Islands Province
10. Task complexity influences the performance of procurement of goods and services which is mediated by job satisfaction in the Riau Islands Province
11. Competence influences the performance of procurement of goods and services which is mediated by job satisfaction in the Riau Islands Province
12. Work culture influences the performance of procurement of goods and services which is mediated by job satisfaction in the Riau Islands Province
13. Locus of control influences the performance of procurement of goods and services which is mediated by job satisfaction in the Riau Islands Province
14. Transformational Leadership moderates job satisfaction and performance in procurement of goods and services in the Riau Islands Province

Method

1. Place and time of research

a) Research Place

This research will be carried out in all OPDs in the Riau Islands Province, which consists of 43 (forty three) Regional Apparatus Organizations.

b) Research Time

The research period lasted for six months, namely from June to November 2024.

2. Research methods

The mixed research model (Mixed Method) consists of a sequential explanatory model, a sequential exploration model, a concurrent triangulation design, and a concurrent embedded model. The sequential explanatory model combines quantitative and qualitative research sequentially, quantitative research is carried out first, then qualitative research is carried out. After the analysis is carried out, the quantitative and qualitative data results will be entered into a matrix to see the comparisons obtained. The sequential exploration model combines both research methods sequentially, starting with qualitative research and the second stage is quantitative research. The concurrent triangulation design is a balanced combination of two research methods using quantitative methods and qualitative methods.

3. Research Population

a) Population

The population is all the objects that will be measured in a study (Cooper and Schindler, 2003: 179). The population of this research is all officials managing the procurement of goods and services in all OPDs of the Riau Islands Province, totaling 163 people. This data is based on data from the Goods and Services Procurement Bureau of Riau Islands Province.

b) Research Sample

The sample is an element of the population chosen to represent the research population (Cooper and Schindler, 2003: 82). In this research, the sample size was adjusted to the analysis model used, namely the Structural Equation Model (SEM).

Results and Discussion

1. Direct Influence

Table 1. Direct Effect

Variabel	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Hypothesis
Work Culture-> Performance of Goods and Services Procurement Employees	0,250	0,247	0,096	2,591	0,010	Accepted
Work Culture -> Job Satisfaction	0,233	0,237	0,110	2,121	0,034	Accepted
Competency -> Performance of Goods and Services Procurement Employees	0,177	0,182	0,092	1,925	0,055	Rejected
Competency -> Job Satisfaction	0,282	0,277	0,117	2,421	0,016	Accepted
Task Complexity -> Performance of Goods and Services Procurement Employees	0,084	0,084	0,075	1,122	0,263	Rejected
Task Complexity -> Job Satisfaction	0,209	0,210	0,077	2,722	0,007	Accepted
Job Satisfaction -> Performance of Goods and Services Procurement Employees	0,252	0,241	0,077	3,274	0,001	Accepted
Locus Of Control -> Performance of Goods and Services Procurement Employees	0,247	0,253	0,116	2,128	0,034	Accepted
Locus Of Control -> Job Satisfaction	0,235	0,236	0,105	2,234	0,026	Accepted

2. Indirect Influence

Table 2. Indirect Effects

Variabel	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Hypothesis
Work Culture -> Job Satisfaction -> Employee Performance in Procurement of Goods and Services	0,059	0,060	0,038	1,559	0,120	Rejected
Competency -> Job Satisfaction -> Performance of Goods and Services Procurement Employees	0,071	0,066	0,032	2,230	0,026	Accepted
Task Complexity -> Job Satisfaction -> Performance of Goods and Services Procurement Employees	0,053	0,049	0,022	2,407	0,016	Accepted
Locus of Control -> Job Satisfaction -> Performance of	0,059	0,058	0,031	1,912	0,056	Rejected

Goods and Services Procurement
 Employees

Table 3. Indirect Effect (Moderating)

VARIABEL	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Hypothesis
Job Satisfaction -> Employee Performance in Procurement of Goods and Services	0,832	0,834	0,035	3,837	0,000	Accepted
Transformational Leadership -> Employee Performance in Procurement of Goods and Services	0,123	0,125	0,037	3,295	0,001	Accepted
Moderating Effect 1 -> Employee Performance in Procurement of Goods and Services	0,017	0,018	0,049	0,345	0,730	Rejected

1) The direct influence between task complexity and job satisfaction has a path coefficient value of 0.209 and a statistical T value of 2.722 > 1.96 (significant). This shows the prediction that if the value of the task complexity variable increases, the job satisfaction variable (Z) will also increase. This determination has a probability value (p-value) of 0.007 < 0.05. This means that if the complexity of the tasks of a job increases, it will actually increase employee job satisfaction, this is because even though the level of complexity and volume of work increases, employees feel happy and their needs are met, which can trigger employees to work well and seriously so that they can improve performance.

2) The direct influence between competence and job satisfaction has a good path coefficient value of 0.282 and a statistical T value of 2.421 > 1.96 which is significant). This shows the prediction that if the value of the competency variable increases, the job satisfaction variable will increase. Where this influence has a probability value (p-value) of 0.016 < 0.05. This finding is in line with McClelland's theory, where the fundamental characteristics possessed by a person have a direct influence on, or can describe, excellent performance. This means that if an employee has a good level of competency it will certainly make them work professionally, working professionally will certainly increase effectiveness and efficiency so that it can improve performance itself.

3) The direct influence between work culture and job satisfaction has a path coefficient value of 0.233 and a statistical T value of 2.121 > 1.96 (significant). This shows the prediction that if the value of the work culture variable increases, the job satisfaction variable (Z) will increase. This influence has a probability value (p-value) of 0.034 < 0.05. Employees who have a good work culture will improve performance, because a good work culture will certainly increase discipline and compliance with laws and regulations.

4) The direct influence between locus of control and job satisfaction has a path coefficient value of 0.235 and a statistical T value of 2.234 > 1.96 (significant). This shows the prediction that if the value of the locus of control variable increases, then the job satisfaction variable will increase. This influence has a probability value (p-value) of 0.026 < 0.05. Employees who have a good locus of control will provide added value for government agencies, because employees who have a good locus of control will provide careful consideration in making decisions.

5) The direct influence between task complexity and procurement employee performance has a path coefficient value of 0.084 and a statistical T value of 1.122 < 1.96 (not significant). This shows the prediction that if the value of the task complexity variable increases, then the procurement employee performance variable will not experience a significant increase. This influence has a probability value (p-value) of 0.263 > 0.05. The performance of procurement employees will increase if the level of work complexity increases, assuming the employee feels happy with the work they are assigned and their needs can be met.

6) The direct influence between competency and performance of procurement employees has a good path coefficient value of 0.177 and a statistical T value of $1.925 < 1.96$ (not significant). This shows the prediction that if the value of the competency variable increases, the performance variable of procurement employees will not experience a significant increase. Employees who have high competence but if it is not accompanied by promising salaries and wages will certainly not improve their performance according to the level of competence they have.

7) The direct influence between work culture and procurement employee performance has a path coefficient value of 0.250 and a statistical T value of $2.591 > 1.96$ (significant). This shows the prediction that if the value of the work culture variable increases, then the procurement employee performance variable will also increase. This influence has a probability value (p-value) of $0.010 < 0.05$. A good employee work culture will certainly have an impact on improving performance. Because a good level of discipline and habits will make the organizational environment conducive so that employees focus on their respective jobs.

8) The direct influence between locus of control and procurement employee performance has a path coefficient value of 0.247 and a statistical T value of $2.128 > 1.96$ (significant). This shows the prediction that if the value of the locus of control variable increases, then the procurement employee performance variable will increase. This influence has a probability value (p-value) of $0.034 < 0.05$. Performance will increase if employees can work well and have emotional intelligence which is complemented by spiritual intelligence.

9) The direct influence between job satisfaction and procurement employee performance has a path coefficient value of 0.252 and a statistical T value of $3.274 > 1.96$ (significant). This shows the prediction that if the value of the job satisfaction variable increases, then the procurement employee performance variable will increase. This influence has a probability value (p-value) of $0.001 < 0.05$. Employees who already have a high level of satisfaction will certainly work seriously and concentrate on their work so that this sincerity will lead to increased performance.

10) The indirect effect between task complexity and procurement employee performance through job satisfaction has a path coefficient value of 0.053 and a statistical T value of $2.407 > 1.96$ (significant). This shows the prediction that if the value of the task complexity variable increases, then the performance of procurement employees through job satisfaction will increase. This influence has a probability value (p-value) of $0.016 < 0.05$. This means that even though the level of work is large and complex, if it is facilitated with good wages and rewards, it will be able to improve employee performance, so it can be categorized as belonging to the type No mediation or no mediation (Barron and Kenny, 1986).

11) The indirect influence between competency and procurement employee performance through job satisfaction has a good path coefficient value of 0.071 and a statistical T value of $2.230 > 1.96$ (significant). This shows the prediction that if the value of the competency variable increases, then the performance of procurement employees through job satisfaction will increase. This influence has a probability value (p-value) of $0.026 < 0.05$. Employees who have a high level of competence and are in line with their work will have a positive impact on increasing performance, plus employee job satisfaction, so it can be categorized as belonging to the type No mediation or no mediation (Barron and Kenny, 1986).

12) The indirect influence between work culture and procurement employee performance through job satisfaction has a good path coefficient value of 0.059 and a statistical T value of $0.559 < 1.96$ (not significant). This shows the prediction that if the value of the work culture variable increases, then the performance of procurement employees through job satisfaction will also increase but not significantly. This influence has a probability value (p-value) of $0.120 > 0.05$. Employees who have a bad work culture will produce bad performance even though they are facilitated with adequate salaries and wages, but bad habits are difficult to correct, so it can be categorized as including full mediation or complete mediation (Barron and Kenny, 1986).

13) The indirect effect between locus of control and procurement employee performance through job satisfaction has a path coefficient value of 0.059 and a statistical T value of $1.912 < 1.96$ (not significant). This shows the prediction that if the value of the locus of control variable increases, then the performance of procurement employees through job satisfaction will increase but not significantly. This influence has a probability value (p-value) of $0.056 > 0.05$. Even though it has been facilitated with adequate salaries and rewards, if the employee's personality is not good, it will not be able to improve the employee's

performance, so it can be categorized as including full mediation or complete mediation (Barron and Kenny, 1986).

14) The indirect influence between job satisfaction on procurement employee performance which is moderated by the transformational leadership variable has a path coefficient value of 0.017 and a statistical T value of 0.345 > 1.96 and has a probability value (p-value) of 0.730 > 0.05 (not significant). This means that the transformational leadership variable as a moderating variable is not able to strengthen the relationship between the job satisfaction variable and the procurement employee performance variable and actually weakens the relationship between the two variables, So according to Solimun (2011), it is included in the type of potential moderating variable (moderator homologizer) because the coefficients B1 and B2 are not significant, This moderating variable does not weaken but strengthens even though it is not significant (0.832 to 0.017) so that the moderating variable, namely transformational leadership, has the potential to become a moderator variable.

Table 4. R-Square Value

Variabel	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Employee Performance in Procurement of Goods and Services	0,907	0,903
Job Satisfaction (Mediation)	0,769	0,763
Moderating Effects	0,775	0,770

R Square Value

- 1) The R Square value of the combined influence of independent or simultaneous variables X1, X2, X3 and No research was carried out by this researcher.
- 2) The R Square value of the combined influence of independent variables and mediating variables on Z1 is 0.763 or 76.30%, which is able to explain the intervening variable, namely job satisfaction and the remaining 23.7% is explained by other variables not discussed in this research.
- 3) The R Square value of the effect of the moderating variable between the job satisfaction variable on the procurement employee performance variable is 0.770 or 77% is able to explain the procurement employee performance variable and the remaining 23% is explained by other variables not examined in this research.

Conclusion

- 1) The direct effect of task complexity on job satisfaction is significant
- 2) The direct influence of competence on job satisfaction is significant
- 3) The direct influence of work culture on job satisfaction is significant
- 4) The direct influence of locus of control on job satisfaction is significant
- 5) The direct influence of task complexity on the performance of procurement employees is not significant
- 6) The direct influence of competency on the performance of procurement employees is not significant
- 7) The direct influence of work culture on the performance of procurement employees is significant
- 8) The direct influence of locus of control on the performance of procurement employees is significant
- 9) The direct influence of job satisfaction on the performance of procurement employees is significant
- 10) The indirect effect of task complexity on procurement employee performance through job satisfaction is significant
- 11) The indirect effect of competency on procurement employee performance through job satisfaction is significant
- 12) The indirect effect of work culture on procurement employee performance through job satisfaction is not significant
- 13) The indirect effect of locus of control on the performance of procurement employees through work leadership is not significant
- 14) The indirect influence of job satisfaction on procurement employee performance which is moderated by transformational leadership is not significant.

Recommendations

1. The Riau Islands Provincial Government is expected to pay more attention to the duties and authority of the PPK, because based on the results of research that there is a parallel relationship between the complexity of tasks and the level of performance achievement of procurement employees, therefore it is recommended that there is a need to separate duties and authority between OPD with PPK or it is better if the position as PPK is held by an apparatus other than the head of OPD, especially for the Head of OPD who does not yet have a procurement certificate or is specifically for physical activities (construction) with a large value.
2. It is recommended to the Riau Islands Provincial Government to immediately improve the qualifications of the PPK, both through technical guidance and through education and training, where the PPK in each OPD currently does not have the qualifications as mandated by the LKPP, so that apart from violating the provisions in question it can also reducing accountability in the management of procurement of goods and services.
3. To improve employee performance in terms of procurement of goods and services, it is very necessary to have habits or norms that must be adhered to or obeyed, therefore work habits or culture are intended to increase compliance with statutory regulations and other technical provisions, so that the process of procuring goods and services in the Riau Islands Province can run in accordance with the mechanisms that have been regulated and determined.
4. Because the procurement of goods and services is full of risks and challenges, it is necessary to have employees/apparatus who have a high personality/locus of control so that it is hoped that all problems faced can be resolved by the employees themselves and it is hoped that they can maintain the level of locus of control. which employees believe can be improved, including by providing work in accordance with the employee's abilities or education, appreciating the performance carried out, and holding training to increase employee motivation and self-confidence so as not to leave all results to fate or luck.
5. The results of measuring the influence of the moderating variable, namely transformational leadership, between job satisfaction and procurement employee performance, with the results of the analysis showing that the transformational leadership variable fails to strengthen or actually weakens the relationship between job satisfaction and procurement employee performance. We suggest that future researchers use this type of Other types of leadership include transactional leadership, behavioral leadership and agile leadership.

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